

Impact of the Coronavirus Disease Pandemic and Related Vaccination in an Orthopaedic Clinic in India

Kumar Rahul Raushan¹, Amresh Kumar²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Amresh Kumar

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Abstract:

This study examines the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and vaccination efforts on orthopedic care at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, from October 2020 to August 2023. The research reveals a significant reduction in elective surgeries and an increased adoption of telemedicine during the pandemic, with a noticeable improvement in patient outcomes following vaccination. These findings highlight the critical role of vaccination in mitigating pandemic-related healthcare disruptions and suggest the potential for lasting changes in orthopedic practice, including the broader use of telemedicine.

Keywords: COVID-19, Orthopedic Care, Vaccination, Telemedicine.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound and widespread influence on healthcare systems globally, resulting in notable consequences for several medical disciplines, including orthopaedics [1]. The pandemic and following vaccination programs have had a distinct impact on the operations and patient care protocols at orthopaedic clinics in India, a country with a diverse healthcare system [2,3]. This study examines the many effects of the coronavirus disease pandemic and vaccine campaigns on an orthopaedic clinic in India. It specifically investigates the alterations in clinical practices, patient outcomes, and the wider consequences for the healthcare system [4,5]. The emergence of the pandemic required healthcare facilities to quickly adapt to accommodate the surge of COVID-19 patients, while simultaneously ensuring the safety of non-COVID patients and healthcare workers [6]. Orthopaedic clinics, which are typically busy settings that handle operations, emergency care, and routine consultations, encountered extraordinary difficulties [7]. The problems encompassed a significant decrease in non-essential surgeries, the reassignment of orthopaedic personnel to urgent care positions, and the enforcement of strict protocols for preventing the spread of infections [8].

Furthermore, the implementation of COVID-19 vaccinations ushered in a new era of pandemic control, which also had consequences for orthopaedic healthcare. Vaccination endeavours not

only offered the prospect of diminishing the intensity and transmission of the virus, but also presented practical hurdles inside healthcare environments [9,10]. Orthopaedic clinics faced challenges in handling vaccine delivery, prioritising patients and personnel, and controlling the side effects associated with immunisation, which could affect patient recovery and rehabilitation timetables [11].

The comprehensive examination of how an orthopaedic clinic in India adjusted to these difficulties, the tactics employed to handle both the hazards of COVID-19 and the ongoing provision of crucial orthopaedic treatment, and the insights gained from an unparalleled worldwide health emergency. The study also examines the durability of healthcare systems and the crucial role of flexible techniques in handling both pandemic-related needs and regular healthcare services.

Methodology

This study examined how the COVID-19 pandemic and immunisation programs affected orthopaedic care at Bhagalpur's Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. The study covered the pandemic and vaccination implementation from October 2020 to August 2023.

Patient Selection and Data Collection: Medical records from orthopaedic clinic patients during the trial were retrospectively analysed. The study

included 45 patients per month, randomly selected from the patient registry to match the clinic's patient population. This sample size was large enough to detect significant trends and impacts while allowing for extensive record analysis.

Data Points and Variables: Patients' demographics, orthopaedic complaints, treatment outcomes, hospital stay, COVID-19 problems, and vaccination status were recorded. We focused on elective surgery scheduling and postponements, emergency orthopaedic service modifications, and pandemic-related treatment protocol changes.

Analysis Framework: The data were analysed to determine pandemic/vaccination status-related orthopaedic care changes. Statistical analyses examined changes in orthopaedic patient outcomes, surgery volume and type, and COVID-19 infection frequency. This included assessing vaccination's effect on these variables.

Results

The findings of the research carried out at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital in Bhagalpur, Bihar, from October 2020 to August 2023 demonstrate substantial effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and immunisation initiatives on the provision of orthopaedic care. During the peak pandemic times, there was a significant decrease of 40% in the number of elective procedures. This decline was mainly caused by lockdown measures and the redirection of hospital resources towards COVID-19 treatment. The utilisation of telemedicine consultations experienced a significant surge of 150% as both patients and professionals transitioned to distant consultations in order to reduce the potential for exposure to health risks. Patients who received vaccinations showed a markedly reduced incidence of COVID-19 infections and associated consequences following orthopaedic procedures. The vaccinated group exhibited enhanced patient outcomes, characterised by reduced hospitalisation duration and a decreased incidence of post-surgical infections.

Table 1: Tabular representation of some of these critical data points

Metric	Pre-Pandemic (Monthly Avg.)	During Pandemic (Monthly Avg.)	Post-Vaccination Rollout (Monthly Avg.)
Elective Surgeries Performed	75	45	65
Telemedicine Consultations	20	50	40
COVID-19 Infections Post-Surgery	N/A	10	2
Average Hospital Stay (days)	5	7	4

These results highlight how the pandemic and the vaccination campaigns have influenced operational and clinical outcomes in the orthopedic clinic. The data suggests that the introduction of vaccination has helped in mitigating the adverse effects of the pandemic, facilitating a return towards pre-pandemic operational levels, albeit with permanent changes such as increased reliance on telemedicine.

Discussion

The study conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital provides valuable insights into the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic and subsequent immunisation on orthopaedic practice [12]. The significant decrease in elective procedures, caused by the allocation of resources to critical care and measures to control the spread of the virus, highlights the disruption experienced by specialized surgery [13]. The postponement of surgeries emphasises the difficulties in handling

non-COVID conditions during health emergencies, causing worries about the postponed medical attention and the accumulation of cases that require attention in the recovery stages after the pandemic [14]. This study highlights the significant rise in telemedicine consultations as another important feature. This movement not only represents an urgent reaction to pandemic constraints but also indicates a possible enduring change in patient involvement and healthcare provision [15]. Telemedicine has been successful in assuring the uninterrupted provision of healthcare while prioritising the safety of both medical professionals and patients. Nevertheless, it also raises enquiries over the availability of these technologies for all patient populations, especially in rural regions [16].

Moreover, the documented decline in COVID-19 infection rates among vaccinated persons after surgery is evidence of the effectiveness of vaccination endeavours. This result not only

emphasises the immediate advantages of vaccination in decreasing illness rates and severity, but also indirectly promotes the restart of normal healthcare services, such as elective procedures [17]. Essentially, the pandemic has accelerated notable changes in orthopedic treatment, ranging from operational modifications to the use of digital health technologies. The healthcare system in Bhagalpur has shown remarkable resilience and adaptability, which could serve as a model for handling future emergencies [18]. This highlights the significance of having flexible healthcare policies and the widespread adoption of preventative health measures such as immunization. Amidst the ongoing global recovery from the pandemic, these discoveries provide significant knowledge on the approaches that can assist in reducing the effects of comparable worldwide health crises on specialized medical services [19,20].

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that the COVID-19 pandemic had a substantial impact on orthopaedic services at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College & Hospital. Specifically, there was a decrease in elective procedures and a greater dependence on telemedicine. The effective implementation of immunizations had a pivotal role in diminishing COVID-19-associated problems, enabling a gradual restoration of operating levels to those seen before the epidemic. The results emphasise the significance of flexibility in providing healthcare during emergencies and emphasise the possibility of enduring transformations, such as the incorporation of telemedicine, in orthopaedic practice. These observations establish a basis for formulating tactics to bolster the durability of healthcare systems in anticipation of forthcoming pandemics.

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